

APPLICATION OF ATMOSPHERIC PLASMA TREATMENTS TO ENHANCE THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF UNSIZED CARBON FIBRE/EPOXY COMPOSITES

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Keywords: Glass fibre, carbon fibre, epoxy composites, atmospheric pressure plasmas

ABSTRACT

The strength of the bond between the resin and fibre reinforcement in a composite is of key importance regarding the control of the latter's mechanical properties. In this study a number of different atmospheric plasma sources are investigated for the activation of both glass and carbon fibres used for the fabrication of composites. The objective is to achieve enhanced fibre/matrix bonding in order to strengthen the resulting epoxy composites mechanical properties. This study evaluated three commercial atmospheric plasma jet sources (PlasmaPen, PlasmaTreat and PlasmaStream), which were used to generate either helium or air discharges. Surface activation of carbon fibre textile presented particular difficulties due to the conducting nature of the fibre. Indeed due to arcing issues with this fibre electrical damage was caused to a helium plasma jet source (PlasmaStream). A further issue was distortion of the fibre bundle by the high jet pressures generated using the PlasmaTreat air plasma source. The optimum source for treating carbon fibre (unsized) was found to be the PlasmaPen, as no arcing or distortion of the fibres was observed with this air plasma jet. Using this source carbon fibre mesh was treated and the resulting composites exhibited a 31.2% increase in inter-laminar shear stress (ILSS) compared with the untreated fibre. A further atmospheric plasma investigation involved the use of a novel reel-to-reel linear argon / oxygen rf plasma source for the treatment of 100 mm widths of the fibre textile. Initial trials with carbon fibre were found to be unsuccessful due to arcing, however this was not found to be a difficulty with glass fibre. At treatment speeds of 5.0 metres min⁻¹ the treated glass fibre was found to yield a 16.9% increase in ILSS compared with the untreated fibre.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to their superior mechanical properties and low weight there is enormous interest in the application of fibre reinforced polymer composites in industries, such as automotive, marine and aerospace [1-4]. Glass fibre is the most commonly used fibre reinforcement in non-aerospace applications such as infrastructure and marine, while carbon fibre is more typically used in advanced composites, particularly aerospace. A critical factor which influences composite performance is the fibre/resin interfacial adhesion [5]. If this adhesion is strong it facilitates for efficient load transfer between fibre and polymer resin, which improves the overall mechanical properties of the composite [6]. Interfacial adhesion is influenced by chemical interactions and mechanical interlocking. Thus poor chemical reactivity at the surface of the fibre reinforcement causes a decrease in adhesion between the fibre and polymer matrix. In an effort to improve interfacial bond strength surface pre-treatment techniques, such as chemical oxidation and the application of sizing layers, are routinely used to modify the fibre surface prior to incorporation with the matrix [7-9]. A further treatment involves the use of plasmas, which activate the fibre surface facilitating the formation of oxygen rich functional chemistries (particularly polar groups such as -COOH), [5-7]. This results in enhanced surface energy (wettability) and can also increase the roughness of the fibres, as a result improving bond strength [10, 11].

The plasma pre-treatment of fibres can be carried out both at low pressure and at atmospheric pressure. Low-pressure sources have drawbacks such as the requirement for expensive vacuum systems for operation and allowing only batch processing of substrates. In contrast atmospheric pressure plasmas allow for high speed and continuous processing and thus can achieve processing cost savings [12].

These plasma treatments have been particularly applied to carbon fibres, as fibre surface is relatively inert and exhibits low surface energies [13, 14]. In contrast to carbon fibres there have been relatively few reports on the use of plasma pre-treatments on glass fibres, this probably reflects the intrinsic higher

surface energy properties of the silicon oxide compared with that of the carbon surfaces. Cech et al [15] showed that low-pressure plasma activation of fibres can modify the surface and improve the fibre/matrix adhesion, by increasing the interlaminar shear strength of glass fibre/polyester composites. While, Krishnamurthy and Kamel [16] indicated argon plasma treatment of glass fibre increased both surface area and wettability.

In this study the research focus is to compare the performance of four commercial air, argon and helium atmospheric plasma sources for the activation of carbon and glass fibre mesh substrates, prior to the fabrication of epoxy composites. The initial focus was on three plasma jet systems, while the continuous treatment of fibre meshes using a reel-to-reel linear plasma source is also evaluated.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

The test substrates used were sized glass fibre which was obtained in the form of a woven tape (0.29 mm thickness) from Glassfibre and Resin Supplies Ltd (Ireland). The carbon fibres were obtained as an unsized unidirectional tow from Goodfellow Cambridge Ltd (UK). The carbon fibres were then hand woven into a mesh of 0.53 mm thickness. (Axis composites, UK). The epoxy resin used was CYCOM® 890 RTM and was obtained from Cytec Industries Inc. (USA). Composites were fabricated by curing the fibre/matrix mixture at 180°C for 2 hours using a pressclave in conjunction with a vacuum bagging lay-up procedure. Silicon wafer and polyethylene terephthalate (PET) test substrates were also used to assist in the evaluation of the activation effectiveness of the plasma source. The silicon wafer was cleaned with acetone in an ultrasonic bath and dried prior to use.

Three atmospheric plasma jet sources were investigated for the treatment of fibres as follows: *PlasmaStream™* (Dow Crowing, Ireland) is an atmospheric pressure discharge created using a modified Plasma Technics Inc. (PTI) 100W RF power supply [17, 18]. The plasma forms between a two metallic pin electrode configurations, at a frequency of 15-25 kHz, when helium (5 Lmin⁻¹) gas is injected between the pins. A Teflon® tube is attached to the orifice of the plasma head, and the plasma exits at the base of the tube. The tube is 75 mm in length and 15 mm in diameter. The working distance from substrate to tube base was approximately 5 mm, and passed over the substrate at a speed of 20 mms⁻¹. In addition to the PTI power supply the PlasmaStream source was also operated using a variable frequency (4-500 kHz) plasma generator G2000 (Redline Technologies). Other than altering frequency, the other processing parameters remained the same.

PlasmaTreat OpenAir atmospheric pressure plasma jet source (PlasmaTreat GmbH, Germany) operating at approximately 22 kHz at an output voltage of 260V [19]. The plasma cycle time was set at 90% with compressed air flow rate of 50 Lmin⁻¹. The PlasmaTreat jet (Figure 1) is mounted onto a CNC system and travels in a raster pattern with a line speed of 250 mms⁻¹ and a step interval of 2 mm. *PlasmaPen* (PVA Tepla, USA) is designed as a hand held device, however for the purpose of this study it was mounted onto a CNC controlled XYZ gantry, to allow for uniform plasma treatments [20]. Jet treatment speed of 40 mms⁻¹ with a step interval of 2 mm was applied. The jet is driven by a 100 Hz bipolar impulse at 5 kV rectified from a 50Hz supply. The compressed air flow rate was 21 Lmin⁻¹.

In addition to the three atmospheric plasma jet sources the performance of a linear rf (13.56 MHz) glow discharge plasma source (SPS Co. Ltd., South Korea) [4], was investigated for the treatment of fibre webs. This source was mounted onto the reel-to-reel Labline™ system manufactured by Dow Corning [21]. The discharge was formed using argon (10-15 Lmin⁻¹) and argon with oxygen (0.03 Lmin⁻¹) gas mixtures. The input power was kept constant at 200W. The treatment area of this plasma was 150 mm in length and approx. 10 mm width. The samples were mounted onto a 10 cm wide glass fibre web using double sided tape, which passed through the treatment chamber at a speed of 5.0 metres min⁻¹.

Figure 1: PlasmaTreat air plasma jet (left) and the reel-to-reel (13.56MHz) argon / oxygen plasma source used to treat 10 cm diameter glass fibre web (right)

Water contact angles were determined using a Dataphysics Instrument OCA 20 system. The water droplet (1 μL) was allowed to rest on the surface for approx. 5 seconds before contact angles were measured. Measurements were obtained from three different points along the sample, and the average of the measurements was determined. Surface energy calculations were determined using three different liquids: deionised water, diodemethane and ethylene glycol. The Owens –Wendt- Rabel- Kaelble (WORK) method was used to measure the surface energy of plasma activated fibres [22, 23].

The morphology of the fibres and composites was examined using a table top TM-1000 Hitachi high-technologies Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM), an Olympus Gx51 Inverted Metallurgical Microscope and Keyence VHX-2000 Series Digital Microscope.

The interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) and flexural strength (σ) of glass/epoxy composites and carbon/epoxy composites for various fibre surface treatments was determined using a three – point bend test as outlined in ASTM D2344. Short beam dimensions had a three point bend range of 9 mm, a beam width of 4 mm and thickness of 2 mm. The short beams were tested using an Instron 8502 servo-hydraulic tensile test machine at room temperature at a speed of 1 mm/min. The inter-laminar shear stress is calculated as follows [24];

$$\text{ILSS} = \frac{3F}{4bt} \quad (1)$$

Where F is the breaking load (N), b and t is the width and thickness of the short beam (mm). The flexural strength of the composite is determined using;

$$\sigma = \frac{2FL}{2bt^2} \quad (2)$$

Where F is the load (N), L is the length of the support span (mm), b and t are the width and thickness (mm).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study was divided into two sections firstly the evaluation of the three atmospheric plasma jet sources for the treatment of carbon fibre bundles and secondly the use of the reel-to-reel linear plasma source for the treatment of the carbon and glass fibre meshes.

3.1 Plasma treatment of carbon fibres

The objective of this study was to evaluate the effectiveness of the PlasmaStream, PlasmaTreat and PlasmaPen atmospheric plasma sources for the activation of carbon fibres. The treatments were carried

out on sized glass and unsized carbon fibre meshes. The meshes (20 x 20 cm) were treated while mounted onto a ceramic plate, while being held in place using a HDPE polymer mesh (hole size 6 mm) as demonstrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: HDPE polymer mesh holding the fibres in place during treatments using the helium plasma source, Redline (left) and the air jet PlasmaPen (right)

During treatment with the helium plasma generated using the *PlasmaStream™* source it was observed that the conductive, irregularly shaped fibre mesh caused severe arcing during treatment. This resulted in severe damage to the fibres mesh and to the plasma source. It was concluded that the arcing was caused by an unsuitable electrode configuration, as there was no well-defined ground with the source. To overcome the arcing issues, the *PlasmaStream™* applicator head was modified to prevent charge build up in the electrode configuration. The modified electrode arrangement involved insulating the source electrode with a thick layer of dielectric material (PET), which also contained a counter electrode. Additionally, the modified source incorporated a variable frequency power called High Voltage Plasma Generator G2000, in the range of 4-500 kHz. Despite the use of variable frequencies, on operation of the helium plasma an excessive amount of power was supplied to the electrode configuration causing arcing along the casing of the electrode (Figure 2).

The *PlasmaTreat Open Air jet source* was then investigated. This was also found to be unsuccessful for fibre activation, as the high pressure of the air plasma jet caused significant distortion of the fibre mesh. Although the fibre mesh was damaged using this source no arcing was observed during plasma treatment.

The *PVA Tepla PlasmaPen air jet source* was then evaluated and was found to be successful at activating the unsized carbon fibre. This source has a broadly similar electrode configuration to that of the PlasmaTreat. Due to the lower air pressure passing through the jet however, no distortion of the fibre mesh was observed. As a result of the carbon fibre treatment using the PlasmaPen a decrease in fibre water contact angle from 103 to 92° was observed after a single pass. The comparison between the ILSS and flexural strengths obtained with composites prepared with activated and unactivated carbon fibres is given in Table 1. As shown in this table as a result of the plasma activation treatment a 32% in ILSS was obtained, while the corresponding increase for Flexural Strength was 23%.

Carbon fibre treatment	ILSS (MPa)	Flexural strength (MPa)
Untreated fibre surface	140.8	1832.4
PlasmaPen – 1 pass both sides of mesh	184.8	2380.2

Table 1: ILSS and flexural strength results obtained for carbon/epoxy composites fabricated using untreated and plasma activated carbon fibre meshes

3.2 Plasma treatment of glass fibre mesh

In this study, the performance of the 13.56 MHz atmospheric source for the reel-to-reel plasma treatment of 100 mm diameter meshes was investigated. Initial studies were carried out using the unsized carbon fibre mesh. Unfortunately significant arcing was observed between the conducting carbon fibres and the linear source and as a result the treatment had to be stopped. A possible explanation for the arcing that occurred during the carbon fibre treatments could be as a result of poor grounding in the plasma source. Presently, the plasma is positioned over an anodised roll, which could be potentially promoting arcing during treatments. The planned future research for the activation of carbon fibre using the linear rf source would involve preforming an optimisation study to eliminate the arcing. This would involve optimising process parameters, such as; varying working distances, treatments speeds and gas composition. This arcing issue, however, was not observed when the sized glass fibre mesh was treated. Initial treatments were carried out using an argon only plasma and subsequently an oxygen containing argon plasma was investigated. It was noted that if the treatment speed increased above 5.0 metres min⁻¹ that some quenching of the plasma occurred. This was due to entrained air being drawn into the plasma within the fibre mesh.

The effect of single, multiple and web back / front treatments were also investigated. In addition to the glass fibre both a fragment of silicon wafer and a PET polymer sheet mounted on the fibre web was also treated to facilitate monitoring of changes in contact angle and surface energy. After treating the test substrates, silicon wafer and PET, the surface energy of both substrates increased as shown in Table 2. The results indicate a significant improvement in the polar contributions which have shown to influence the interfacial adhesion of fibre/matrix bonding. With the addition of oxygen (0.03 Lmin⁻¹) into the argon (15 Lmin⁻¹) plasma there was an increase in the polar contribution of the activated silicon and PET.

Substrate	WCA (°)	γ (mN/m)	γ^d (mN/m)	γ^p (mN/m)
Silicon wafer – untreated	52	48.4	29.7	18.7
Silicon wafer – argon plasma treated	<5	68.7	35.4	33.3
Silicon wafer – argon/oxygen plasma treated	<5	68.5	28.6	40.0
PET – untreated	92	34.1	36.3	0.75
PET – argon plasma treated	40	58.5	37.0	21.6
PET – argon/oxygen plasma treated	34	62.3	38.6	23.8

Table 2: Water contact angle (WCA) and surface energy (γ) measurements of untreated and plasma treated silicon wafer and PET, in addition to dispersive (γ^d) and polar (γ^p) contributions

To determine the effects of the plasma treatment on the fibre surfaces and subsequently on that of the fabricated composites, three point bend tests were performed. Inter-laminar shear stress and flexural strength were calculated as detailed in the experimental section, the results of this study are given in Table 3.

Glass fibre treatment	ILSS (MPa)	Flexural strength (MPa)
Untreated fibre surface	43.4	801.5
Argon plasma (10 Lmin ⁻¹), 1 pass	48.7	901.4
Argon plasma (10 Lmin ⁻¹), 1 pass both sides of ply	50.8	924.9
Argon/oxygen plasma (15 Lmin ⁻¹ /0.03 Lmin ⁻¹), 1 pass both sides of ply	50.8	962.1

Table 3: ILSS and flexural strength results of the untreated glass fibre and treated glass/epoxy composites

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study the atmospheric plasma treatment of carbon and glass fibre meshes prior to composite formation were investigated. Three atmospheric plasma sources, PlasmaStream, PlasmaTreat and PlasmaPen were evaluated for the plasma activation of unsized carbon fibre surfaces. It was concluded that the PlasmaPen atmospheric jet source was the most suitable source for treating unsized carbon fibre as no arcing or distortion of the fibres was observed. Epoxy composites fabricated using PlasmaPen air plasma activate of carbon fibre meshes exhibited a 32% and 23.0% increase in ILSS and flexural strength respectively, compared with that obtained for the untreated fibres.

For continuous treatment of fibre meshes a reel-to-reel source is a potential alternative to multiple plasma jets. The performance of a 15 cm diameter linear rf plasma source (SPS Co. Ltd) was investigated. Based on initial trials carried out using PET test pieces mounted on the fibre web the addition of oxygen into the argon plasma resulted in an increased rate of activation. The treatment of carbon fibre was found to be unsuccessful with this source due to arcing; this however was not a difficulty with glass fibre. A treatment speed of 5.0 metres min⁻¹ was used for the 10 cm diameter glass fibre mesh. The optimum increase in ILSS of 16.9% and flexural strength by 20.0% compared with the untreated fibre, was obtained where the mesh was treated on both sides with the plasma. Based on this preliminary study this linear plasma source has a significant potential to increase the mechanical performance of glass fibre composites.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was partially funded by the Science Foundation Ireland MaREI Centre.

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